

Integrating torrefaction of pulp industry sludge with anaerobic digestion to produce bioenergy and biochemicals: Techno-economic and environmental feasibility analysis

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ABSTRACT

In order to improve the economic competitiveness of bioenergy carriers and biochemicals, they must be produced from low-cost or no-cost feedstock and at a reduced operational expenses. In that regard, this study focused on understanding the techno-economic feasibility of using pulp sludge as a low-cost alternative feedstock to forestry biomass in torrefaction. Economic feasibility of further integrating pulp sludge torrefaction with anaerobic digestion to produce energy, biomethane and volatile fatty acids (VFA) was also studied. The operational expenses were around 8.2 and 2.04 M€ and the minimum selling price of torrefied pellets was 407 and 189 €/t for forestry biomass torrefaction and pulp sludge torrefaction respectively. In case of integrated approaches, VFA production showed higher economic feasibility with a torrefied pellets selling price of 163 €/t compared with biomethane production (213 €/t). The biomethane and VFA selling price can be reduced by 90 and 64% compared with current market price at torrefied pellets selling price of 260 €/t. Sensitivity analysis revealed that, moisture content of the sludge is the main influencing parameter on the overall economic feasibility of the pulp sludge torrefaction. The environmental analysis showed that pulp sludge torrefaction has higher emissions compared with forestry biomass torrefaction.

1. Introduction

Globally, energy and chemical industries are the major industries in terms of economy, resource utilization, and employment. The total sales value of global chemical industry in 2020 was around €3.5 trillion and is expected to reach €6.2 trillion by 2030 [1]. The chemical industry supported more than 120 million jobs globally in 2019 [2]. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA), the investments in energy sector could reach to 2.4 trillion in 2022 [3]. Although, energy and chemical industry are the driving forces of the global economy, both the industries are heavily dependent on fossil resources, which are responsible for greenhouse gasses and ultimately associated with environmental impacts. According to Kähler et al. [4], the chemical industry consumes around 14% of oil and 8% of natural gas in the global supply, which is equal to around 723 megatons of carbon. In energy sector, in 2019, around 81% of world energy was produced from fossil fuels [5].

On the other hand, under its “Roadmap for moving to a competitive low-carbon economy in 2050”, EU sets ambitious targets to reduce its greenhouse gasses by 85 – 90% compared to 1990 level [6]. Recently

under COP26, several countries have agreed to reduce our dependency on coal in energy production. In order to achieve these ambitious targets, reducing the dependency on fossil resources in both chemical and energy industries is needed. The energy consumption in EU chemical industry has reduced by 21% since 1990 because of improved energy efficiency of the production processes [7]. In parallel, the power sector is also being decarbonized through the rapid inclusion of solar and wind energy. However, fossil resources are still the starting feedstock for many chemical building blocks and in energy production. Thus, there is a need to find alternative carbon feedstock to produce both energy carriers and chemicals.

Recently, biomass has evolved as an alternative carbon source to the fossil resources. However, the commercial scale production of energy and chemicals from biomass is not yet economically feasible without subsidies. The main reasons are the higher feedstock prices and operational costs. Industrial valorization of biomass in large quantities is also under a question. Furthermore, the demand for woody biomass from conventional applications like construction and furniture sectors is also continuously increasing. Hence, it is necessary to find alternative

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resources to biomass to produce bioenergy and biochemicals with improved economic and environmental feasibility. Additionally, sharing resources between different industries and processes could also help further optimize the overall feasibility of the bio-based processes.

Organic wastes, like pulp industry sludge could be such an alternative material to both fossil resources and forestry wood for chemicals and energy production. Pulp industry sludge is the organic residue produced during the treatment of wastewater from pulping process [8]. Depending on the type of wastewater treatment, pulp sludge can be divided into primary and secondary sludge. To understand the scale of sludge production, the total pulp production in Europe in 2021 was around 37.3 million tons [9]. Generally, 40 – 50 kg of dry sludge is produced per ton of pulp produced. The composition and physico-chemical properties of the sludge vary depending on the pulping and wastewater treatment approaches. Pulp industry sludge mainly contains undigested fibers, wood chips, sand, metals, plastics and grit. Commonly, pulp sludge is managed through landfilling, spreading in agricultural fields, composting after mixing with other wood wastes, or energy recovery through incineration and anaerobic digestion [8]. However, all these methods have their own operational challenges. For example, landfilling of organic residues is banned and/or restricted in several countries. Because of the inhibitory compounds and high ash, the specific methane yield and rate of methane production is lower in case of anaerobic digestion of pulp industry sludge. At the same time, handling of digestate is also a challenge. The readers are guided to [8] for a more detailed view on the challenges in handling pulp industry sludge.

On the other hand, in the last decade torrefaction has evolved as a pretreatment process to improve the fuel characteristics of the lignocellulosic biomass. However, the economic feasibility of the torrefied pellets is lower when produced from forestry wood. Although the primary intention of the torrefaction process was to produce coal equivalent pellets in terms of fuel characteristics, alternatively torrefaction process can also be used as a central process to produce bioenergy carriers and biochemicals.

Connecting the above discussed challenges and opportunities recently, our group has reported [10] an alternative integrated process to produce torrefied pellets, biogas and volatile fatty acids (VFA) from pulp industry sludge. The authors observed significantly higher methane and VFA yield compared with conventional processes. Although, the experimental results are interesting, the scale-up and commercial success of such processes depend on the techno-economic feasibility.

In that regard, for the first time, this study focused on the techno-economic feasibility of integrating torrefaction of pulp industry sludge with anaerobic digestion. The mass and energy balances of commercial scale process were developed. Different scenarios of biogas applications, like energy production through engine, and upgraded biomethane to gas grid were evaluated. The comparative analysis between biomethane production and volatile fatty acids production was also carried out. The economic feasibility was evaluated using different economic indicators, such as minimum selling price (MSP), net present value (NPV), internal rate on return (IRR) and cash flow. The influence of different operating parameters on the economic feasibility was analyzed through sensitivity analysis. The only previous study [11] on the techno-economic feasibility of integrating torrefaction and anaerobic digestion was focused only on biomethane production and considered pine wood chips as a feedstock. To the knowledge of the authors, this is the first study on the techno-economic feasibility of pulp sludge torrefaction, and integrating it with anaerobic digestion to produce biomethane and VFA.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Process configuration and different scenarios

The dewatered pulp sludge was considered as a feedstock to produce torrefied pellets. For comparative analysis, wet wood chips were also

considered as a feedstock. A torrefaction process in the order of feedstock drying, torrefaction, torrefied biomass cooling, grinding, and pelleting was considered.

For the standalone torrefaction (Case1 and Case2), the combustion of torrefaction volatiles together with utility fuel to produce heat energy required for the process was considered. The difference between Case1 and Case2 was with feedstock, for Case1 wet forestry wood chips and for Case2 dewatered pulp industry sludge was considered. For Integrated approaches, i.e. Case3 to Case6, condensation of torrefaction volatiles to produce torrefaction condensate and later using it in AD as a substrate was considered. Methane production was considered for Case3 and Case4. The VFA production was considered for Case5 and Case6. The difference between Case3 and Case4 was the end application of biogas. The energy production using engine, and selling the upgraded biomethane to gas grid was considered for Case3 and Case4, respectively. In Case 6, it was assumed that the uncondensed volatiles are combusted in existing boiler in the pulp mill. For Case6, it was also considered that the heat energy required for drying and torrefaction is supplied by the pulp mill. The possible heat energy recovery options were considered in all the cases.

2.2. Process parameters

The mass and energy flows were calculated for a plant capacity of 60,000 tons of wet sludge per year. The experimental results from our previous studies on pulp sludge torrefaction [12] and anaerobic digestion of pulp sludge derived condensate [10] was used as a base to simulate the product flow at each stage of the process for the selected capacity of the plant. The moisture content of the wood chips was selected as 40%.

2.2.1. Dewatering and drying

The pulp industry sludge from wastewater treatment plant contains dry solid content of <10%. In this study, it was assumed that sludge is mechanically dewatered to a moisture content of 60% and supplied by the pulp mills. Because of its high moisture content, a belt type dryer was considered to dry the pulp sludge. It was assumed that both pulp sludge and wood chips are thermally dried at 110 °C to a moisture level of 10% in the dried product. For energy balance, it was assumed that both dried sludge and the water vapor leaves the dryer at 110 °C. The methodology presented in [12] was followed to calculate the drying energy requirement.

2.2.2. Torrefaction

Dried pulp sludge and wood chips with a moisture content of 10% was considered as a feedstock for torrefaction. Because of the higher condensate yield, the torrefaction operating temperature was considered as 300 °C. The energy required for torrefaction was calculated following the methodology presented in [11]. The mass yield of pulp sludge torrefaction products were considered based on our previous study [10], which are around 0.55, 0.3, 0.15 kg/kg of dry sludge for torrefied sludge, torrefaction condensate and un-condensed volatiles, respectively. It was considered that torrefaction products leave the reactor at torrefaction operating temperature.

2.2.3. Pellets production

The pellets production follows the sequence as, torrefied biomass cooling, grinding, screening, pelleting, screening and storage. Torrefied biomass cooling to 50 °C prior to grinding was considered. As suggested by [11], steam at a flow rate of 0.15 kg per kg of torrefied biomass was considered as a binding agent. The electrical energy required for pellet mill (i.e. grinding, pelleting, and screening) was considered as 550 kJ/kg of torrefied biomass. It was assumed that the loss of material at pellet mill is negligible.

2.2.4. Anaerobic digestion

The mass and energy balances and sizing of anaerobic digestion was carried out according to the methodology presented in [11] and [13]. The AD operating temperature was selected as 35 °C. The specific methane and VFA yield of the condensate was selected as 70 mL/g of torrefaction condensate and 2 g/g VS respectively [10]. The electrical energy potential of biomethane was selected as 10 kWh/m³ [11]. The electrical efficiency of the engine was selected as 45%. The high pressure water scrubbing was considered for biogas purification. In case of VFA recovery, the multi-step solvent extraction presented by [14] was considered. As the condensate is highly inhibitory to the AD, diluting it with water at a rate of 50% was considered. Thus, the total liquid flow (i. e. torrefaction condensate + diluting water) was considered in the calculation of AD digester volume.

2.2.5. Heat energy recovery

As presented previously [11], four different heat energy recovery options such as from dryer water vapor, torrefied biomass cooling, torrefaction volatiles condensation, and from biogas engine were considered in this study. The heat energy recovery efficiency from biogas engine was considered as 50% [11]. Using a part of recovered heat energy for pre-heating the sludge from 20 to 50 °C before drying was considered. Routing a part of recovered heat energy to maintain AD digester temperature was also considered. The heat energy available after in-house consumption (i.e. sludge preheating and AD digester heating) was considered for district heating.

2.2.6. Wastewater treatment

In general, digestate is used as a fertilizer in agricultural application. As the considered substrate for the AD process is in liquid state, the solid fraction in the digestate cannot be compared with the digestate from conventional AD process. Thus, in this study digestate is considered as a wastewater, which needs to be treated before releasing into the environment. The treatment of condensed water after heat energy recovery from drying vapors is also considered.

2.3. Economic analysis

2.3.1. Total capital investment (TCI)

The total capital investment was calculated by combing all the investments presented in Eq. (1).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total capital investment} = & \text{fixed capital investment (investment on equipment} \\ & + \text{site and building)} + \text{engineering and supervision} \\ & + \text{contingency} + \text{working capital} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The fixed capital investment (FCI) is the sum of the total capital investment on equipment (CIE), land and buildings. The equipment costs collected from the literature are adjusted to the operating size of this study using the Eq. (2).

$$C_n = C_i \times \left(\frac{S_n}{S_i} \right)^n \quad (2)$$

Where C_n and C_i are new and initial costs, S_n and S_i are the capacity of new equipment and base equipment, respectively, n is the power factor, which commonly varies between 0.6 and 0.8 [15].

The costs are adjusted to the currency conversion data with respect to the specific year. The calculated equipment costs are also further adjusted to the inflation by using chemical engineering plant cost index (CEPCI) according to the Eq. (3) [15]. The CEPCI for July i.e. 831.7 was used in this study [16,17].

$$\text{Cost}_{\text{year } x} = \text{Cost}_{\text{year } y} \times \frac{\text{CEPCI}_y}{\text{CEPCI}_x} \quad (3)$$

The costs of the major equipment were collected from literature [11,

18]. The cost of AD digester was considered as 500 USD/m³ [19]. The boiler capital cost was selected from [18]. The capital investment for biogas upgrading and VFA recovery were selected from [20] and [14] respectively. The site and building costs were selected as €500,000. The other capital costs were selected as following [11]

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Startup expenses} &= 10\% \text{ of CIE} \\ \text{Engineering and supervision} &= 12\% \text{ CIE,} \\ \text{Contingency} &= 10\% \text{ of CIE} \\ \text{Working capital} &= 15\% \text{ of FCI} \end{aligned}$$

2.3.2. Production costs

The utility costs were calculated according to the data presented in Table 1. It was assumed that plant operates for 8000 h per year with three shifts of 8 working hours. The expenses other than utilities were calculated according to the methodology presented by [11] and [15], and as presented below

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Supervising staff costs} &= 15\% \text{ of operating labor;} \\ \text{Maintenance and repair} &= 3\% \text{ of FCI;} \\ \text{Factory over heads} &= 70\% \text{ of operating labor} + 30\% \text{ FCI;} \end{aligned}$$

At the time of this study, the wet wood chips prices in the Baltic countries were varying between 85 and 130 €/t [21], and a price of 100 €/t was selected in this study. Today, the electricity prices in Estonia are highly fluctuating and are exceptionally high. Thus, as a common price of 100 €/MWh was selected for this study. The heat energy price was considered as 60 €/MWh according to the data from heat energy supplier in the Tartu region, Estonia [22]. The wastewater treatment costs were considered according to the industrial price of local wastewater treatment plant facility, which was around 3 €/m³. The operational costs for biogas purification was considered as 0.2 €/m³ [11]. The operational costs for VFA recovery was considered as 0.6 €/kg of feed [14,23,24]. The operating labor costs are considered as 10 €/h. The straight-line method over 10 years was considered for depreciation.

2.3.3. Feasibility analysis

The economic feasibility of the proposed process was analyzed through different indicators such as minimum selling price (MSP), net present value (NPV) and cash flow, internal rate of return (IRR), and payback period. All these economic indicators were calculated according to the methodology presented in [11] and using the Eqs. (4) – (9). Briefly, the MSP of torrefied biomass (TB) pellets was calculated iteratively, where total operational costs are equal to the total revenue. The IRR values were calculated iteratively by equating NPV to zero and by adjusting the i value. The sensitivity analysis was carried out by varying the operating parameters by ±25%.

$$\text{NPV} = \left(\frac{(1+i)^n - 1}{i \times (1+i)^n} \times \text{net cash flow} \right) - \text{TCI} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{net cash flow} = ((\text{TR} - \text{PC}) * (1 - \text{tax rate})) + \text{D} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{TR} = \text{PC} + \text{ROI} + \text{IT} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{ROI} = \text{CRF} \times \text{TCI} \quad (7)$$

Table 1

The various costs considered for the economic evaluation.

Utility	Cost (€)	Reference
Wet wood chips (forest) (€/MWh)	40	[21]
Electrical energy purchasing price (€/MWh)	100	[25]
Steam as binding agent (€/t)	22	[15]
Operating labor wages (€/hour)	10	
Electrical energy selling price (€/MWh)	100	[25]
District heat selling price (€/MWh)	60	[22]
Biomethane selling price (€/m ³)	1.5	[26]
Biomethane upgrading costs (€/m ³ of biogas)	0.2	[20]
Volatile fatty acids recovery costs (€/kg of liquid flow)	0.6	[14]

$$IT = \text{taxation rate} \times (TR - PC - D) \quad (8)$$

$$CRF = \frac{i \times (1 + i)^n}{(1 + i)^n - 1} \quad (9)$$

Where TR is the total revenue (€), which includes the revenue from all the sources in the process. PC is the total production cost (€) and D is the depreciation. ROI is the return on investment (€), CRF is the capital recovery factor and TCI is the total capital investment (€). IT is the income tax (€) which was selected as 20%, and i is the discount rate, which was selected as 7%.

2.4. Life cycle assessment

The system boundaries for life cycle analysis (LCA) was set as presented in Fig. 1. The cradle-to-gate and gate-to-gate approaches were considered for forestry biomass and pulp sludge torrefaction, respectively. The functional unit was selected as one ton of torrefied biomass

pellets production. The process description follows the same as presented in Section 2.1 for different cases. The mass and energy data calculated in this study for selected capacity were used as a base for inventory analysis for majority of the unit operations. The emissions value for wood chips production was selected as 0.05 kg CO₂ eq./kg of wood chips [27]. The emissions value for electrical energy (Estonia) was selected as 0.54,689 kg of CO₂ eq./kWh [28]. The literature review shows that emissions for wastewater treatment vary between 0.22 and 0.33 kg CO₂ eq./m³ [29,30]. In this study, the emissions value for wastewater was selected as 0.3 kg CO₂ eq./m³. The emissions from the combustion of torrefaction volatiles and the utility fuel (dried wood chips and pulp sludge) were calculated through stoichiometric combustion equations. The transportation distance of wood chips was selected as 100 km. The emissions for transportation was selected as 0.1 kg CO₂/km-t [31,32]. The emission data was presented in terms of global warming potential (GWP).

Fig. 1. The system boundary for life cycle analysis (a) standalone forestry biomass torrefaction (Case1) (b) pulp sludge standalone torrefaction (Case2) (c) Pulp sludge torrefaction integrated with anaerobic digestion (Case3 to Case5) (d) Pulp sludge torrefaction integrated with anaerobic digestion and existing pulp industry for heat energy (Case6).

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Mass and energy flows

The mass and energy balances for different scenarios are presented in Fig. 2. The energy consumption in drying process is the major difference between the woody biomass based torrefaction (Case1) and pulp sludge based torrefaction (Case2 – Case5). The drying energy required for Case2 to Case6 was around 2040 kJ/kg and the same for Case1 was around 1350 kJ/kg, which is 51% lower. From the Fig. 2 it can also be observed that, the torrefied biomass pellets (TB pellets) flow rate was also varied significantly between forestry biomass torrefaction and pulp sludge torrefaction. Although the feedstock flowrate is common (i.e. 7.05 t/h), the final TB pellets flow rate was around 2.94 and 1.67 t/h for Case1 and Case2, respectively. The higher moisture content in the sludge is the main reason for the increased drying energy requirement and reduced product yield in case of pulp sludge torrefaction compared with

forestry biomass torrefaction. In this study, the dried biomass was considered as a utility fuel to combust together with torrefaction volatiles to produce heat energy required for the process. Because of the higher drying energy requirement, the dried sludge flow rate to the boiler was higher for Case2–5 compared with Case1. The utility fuel flow rate at selected operating conditions was around 0.08 t/h and 0.33 t/h, respectively for Case1 and Case2. The condensation of torrefaction volatiles to produce torrefaction condensate and combustion of uncondensed volatiles together with utility fuel (dried sludge) was considered for Case3 – Case5. Thus, the dried sludge flow rate (0.77 t/h) as utility fuel was higher for Case3 and Case4 compared with Case2 (0.33 t/h). The heat demand is higher for Case5 compared with Case3 and Case4 because of additional heat energy requirement for VFA recovery. Thus, the dried sludge flow rate to boiler is higher than Case3 and Case4, which is around 0.89 t/h. In contrast to Case3 to Case5, for Case6 it was considered that the uncondensed volatiles are combusted in the existing boiler at pulp mill and the heat energy required for drying and

Fig. 2. Mass and energy balances for different scenarios. Case1 and Case2 = forestry biomass and pulp sludge standalone torrefaction, respectively. Case3 to Case6 = pulp sludge torrefaction integrated with anaerobic digestion; Case3 = energy production from biogas using engine, Case4 = biogas upgrading to biomethane, Case5 = volatile fatty acids production (VFA), Case6 = VFA production and heat energy supply from pulp mill.

torrefaction is supplied back. Thus, no utility fuel requirement was considered for Case6 and relatively, the final yield of TB pellets (1.86 t/h) was higher compared with Case2 and Case3–5. The torrefaction volatiles flow rate was 2.16, 1.32, 1.13 and 1.47 t/h for Case1, Case2, Case3–5 and Case6 respectively. The torrefaction condensate flow rate was around 0.77 and 1.0 t/h for Case3–5 and Case6, respectively.

The calculated AD digester volume was 1035, 1315 and 1350 m³ for Case3–4, Case5 and Case6 respectively. The total biogas produced was 1835 m³/day for Case3 and Case4 respectively. The final methane yield after purification was 1207 m³/day for Case4. The electrical and heat energy produced from engine for Case3, was 0.21 MW and 0.26 MW respectively. It was assumed that around 5% of the electrical energy produced is used for operating the AD. The final net electrical energy available was around 0.20 MW

As presented in Section 2, heat energy recovery from dryer vapors, torrefied biomass cooling, torrefaction volatiles condensation and from engine was considered. A part of heat energy was considered for sludge preheating to 50 °C and to maintain the digester at 35 °C. The net total heat energy available was 1.01, 1.77, 2.07, 1.80, and 1.86 MW for Case1, Case2, Case3, Case4–5 and Case6 respectively.

The wastewater flow rate is another parameter significantly different between forestry biomass based torrefaction (Case1) and pulp sludge based torrefaction (Case2). The total amount of water evaporating during drying was 4.17 and 2.5 t/h for Case1 and Case2, respectively. The wastewater flow for Case2 and Case3–6 within the pulp sludge torrefaction was also different because of the additional wastewater flow from AD. The total wastewater flow for standalone torrefaction i.e. Case1 and Case2 was around 2.5, and 4.17 t/h respectively. The wastewater flow from pulp sludge torrefaction was 1.66% higher than that of forestry biomass torrefaction. The wastewater flowrate for Case3–5 and Case6 was 5.29, 5.63 t/h, respectively. The total electrical energy required to run the dryer was 600 and 1000 MWh per year for Case1 and Case2, respectively.

3.2. Economic analysis

3.2.1. Total capital investment

The breakdown of capital investment for different scenarios is presented in Table 2. The capital costs for standalone torrefaction i.e. Case1, Case2 was 18.37 and 16.64 M€ (million €). The capital costs for integrated torrefaction was 18.64, 18.88, 20.44 and 19.22 M€ for Case3, Case4, Case5 and Case6 respectively. In the integrated processes, the lower capital investment was observed for Case6 compared with Case5. This is mainly because of the reduced investment on boiler, as the energy

is supplied by the existing pulp mill. Although Case3, Case4, and Case5 have additional investment on AD, biogas processing, and VFA recovery, the total investment costs are still in the range of Case1. From Table 2, it can be observed that the cost of the torrefaction reactor is the influencing parameter in the total capital invest for all the scenarios. The share of the torrefaction reactor in the total fixed capital investment was 36%, 30%, 28%, 25% and 27% for Case1, Case2, Case3–5 and Case6, respectively. Previously, studies [33] and [11] reported that torrefaction reactor alone costs around 34 and 50% of total investment respectively.

The capital investment per ton of torrefied biomass pellets could give better understanding on the capital investment. The capital investment costs are 779, 1238, 1627, 1648, 1873 and 1287 €/t for Case1, Case2, Case3, Case4, Case5, and Case6 respectively. Previously, [34] reported a capital investment of 895 €/t for a road side grass based torrefaction including washing and anaerobic digestion with a plant capacity of 11, 101 tons of TB pellets production per year. Another study [11], observed a capital invest of around 524 €/t for a torrefaction process integrated with AD with a plant capacity of 79,200 tons of TB pellets. The investment costs for AD including end application of biogas was 1.21, 1.37 M€ for Case3 (engine) and Case4 (biomethane), respectively. In case of VFA production, the combined investment on AD and VFA recovery was around, 2.52 and 2.59 M€ for Case5 and Case6, respectively, which is 794 and 596 €/kg VFA-day.

3.2.2. Production costs

The breakdown of total production costs for different scenarios are presented in Fig. 3. The total manufacturing costs are 8.23, 2.05, 2.23, 2.36, 3.03, 3.29 M€ for Case1, Case2, Case3, Case4, Case5 and Case6, respectively. As expected, compared with pulp sludge standalone torrefaction (Case2), biomass torrefaction (Case1) showed higher operational costs (75% higher). This is mainly because of the additional expenditure on feedstock. Generally, for wood chips based torrefaction, the feedstock costs accounted for 50 – 80% [11]. In this study, the feedstock price for Case1 accounted for around 74%. In case of pulp sludge based torrefaction, the feedstock costs are zero, as the pulp sludge is supplied by pulp mill at no price. In case of pulp sludge torrefaction, Case2 has lower operational expenses compared with integrated approaches i.e. Case3 – Case6. This is mainly because of increased operational costs with downstream processing of biogas and VFA. Again, when compared with biogas purification (Case4), VFA recovery (Case5) showed higher operational costs. In addition to feedstock, manpower and factory overheads are significant costs for standalone torrefaction, which account for 10 and 45% for Case1 and Case2, respectively. In case of integrated approaches, the operational costs of biogas purification

Table 2
Total capital investment for different cases.

Equipment	Case1	Case2	Case3	Case4	Case5	Case6
Drying	2958,828	2, 958, 828	2958,828	2958,828	2958,828	2958,828
Torrefaction	6671,037	5, 047, 053	4617,620	4617,620	4495,155	5355,828
Pelletizing	455,859	403, 917	390,087	390,087	388,758	412,392
Boiler	1522,068	1, 807, 225	1807,225	1807,225	1807,225	0
Condensate production	0	0	550,000	550,000	550,000	550,000
Anaerobic digestion	0	0	999,627	999,627	1581,829	1486,947
Engine	0	0	215,446	0	0	0
Biogas purification	0	0	0	371,844	0	0
Volatile fatty acids recovery	0	0	0	0	943,060	1105,617
Heat exchangers for energy recovery	242,708	242,708	245,533	245,533	245,533	292,922
Site and buildings	500,000	500,000	500,000	500,000	500,000	500,000
Total investment on equipment + sites and building	12,107,792	10,962,701	12,284,367	12,440,764	13,470,386	12,662,534
Other capital investment						
Engineering and supervision cost	1452,935	1315,524	1474,124	1492,892	1616,446	1519,504
Startup expenses	1210,779	1096,270	1228,437	1244,076	1347,039	1266,253
Contingency	1210,779	1096,270	1228,437	1, 244, 076	1347,039	1266,253
Total fixed capital investment	15,982,285	14,470,765	16,215,364	16,421,809	17,780,910	16,714,545
Working capital	2397,343	2170,615	2432,305	2463,271	2667,137	2507,182
Total Capital investment	18,379,628	16,641,380	18,647,668	18,885,080	20,448,047	19,221,727

(Case4) and VFA recovery (Case5) costs are around 5 and 21% of total production costs respectively. Previously, [33] observed the same phenomenon that feedstock costs and operating labor are the influencing parameters in the manufacturing costs for the conventional torrefaction process.

3.2.3. Economic feasibility

3.2.3.1. Minimum selling price. The Fig. 4a shows the minimum selling price (MSP) of TB pellets for different scenarios. As expected, the MSP of biomass based torrefaction is significantly higher compared with other cases. This is mainly because of increased operational expenses as presented in Section 3.2.2. For example, the MSP of TB pellets for standalone torrefaction was 407 and 189 €/t for biomass torrefaction (Case1) and pulp sludge torrefaction (Case2), respectively. The MSP of Case1 was 54% higher than the Case2. In case of integrated approaches, the MSP of TB pellets was 221, 213, 163, and 72 €/t for Case3, Case4, Case5, and Case6, respectively. Interestingly, although, there is an additional revenue from biogas, the MSP of Case3 and Case4 are higher than standalone pulp sludge torrefaction (Case1). This has mainly because of two reasons, one is higher operational expenses and investment costs. The second reason is lower revenue from torrefied pellets; as a part of the dried material is used as a utility fuel (refer Fig. 1), the TB pellets yield and ultimately the revenue from TB pellets is relatively lower in case of Case3, and Case4. However, Case5 showed lower MSP compared with Case2, Case3 and Case4. The MSP value of Case5 was 163 €/t, which is 14%, 26% and 23% less than Case2, Case3, and Case4,

respectively. This is mainly because of higher revenue from VFA. The MSP values were further reduced to 72 €/t for Case6, where it was considered that process energy required is supplied by the existing pulp mill. The higher product flowrate compared with all other cases was the main reason for lower MSP value for Case6. As energy is supplied from pulp mill, there is no need to use a part of dried sludge as utility fuel and investment costs on boiler are also reduced.

Previous studies reported minimum selling price of TB pellets in the range of 170 – 300 €/t [11,33,35] which is lower than the value observed for standalone torrefaction (Case1) in this study. This is mainly because of the higher feedstock prices and higher investment costs. Today, the forestry biomass price is unusually high and because of the inflation, the total capital investment costs are relatively higher in this study compared with previous studies.

3.2.3.2. Internal rate of return (IRR). The IRR is one of the financial indicator commonly used to compare the economic feasibility of different investment options. The higher the IRR value, the higher the project feasibility. The IRR values for TB pellets selling price in the range of 140 – 260 €/t is presented in Fig. 5a. For biomass torrefaction (Case1), the TB pellets selling price of less than 407 €/t is not feasible to recover the initial capital investment. Thus, the IRR values for Case1 is not presented in Fig. 5a. The IRR values were in the range of 4% to 20%. In case of pulp sludge torrefaction, Case3 and Case4 showed lower IRR values, especially for selling price of TB pellets less than 200 €/t. For both, Case2 and Case5, the IRR values were around 10% at TB pellets selling price of 220 €/t. For Case6, the IRR values reached 15% at TB

Fig. 3. Production costs for different cases.

Fig. 4. The minimum selling price (MSP) of torrefied biomass pellets and the revenue at the respective selling price (a) minimum selling price (b) revenue per year.

pellets selling price already at 180 €/t.

3.2.3.3. Net present value (NPV). The Fig. 5b shows the NPV values of different Cases at varied pellets selling price. From the same figure, it can be observed that, the NPV values of Case1 is negative at all the selected TB pellets selling price. Thus, at this price Case1 is not at all profitable. The same can also be observed from MSP value of Case1, which was around 407 €/t. Integrated approaches, Case3 and Case4 showed negative NPV values when TB pellets selling price was less than 180 €/t. The Case5 and Case6 showed higher NPV values compared with other cases.

3.2.3.4. Cash flow. The Fig. 6 shows the cumulative cash flow of different scenarios over a project period of 20 years. As the minimum selling price of TB pellets is 407 €/t, the cash flow for Case1 is presented for TB pellets selling price of 450 €/t. For the pulp sludge torrefaction (i. e. Case2 – Case6), the selling price of pellets was selected as 220 €/t. Although the selling price of forestry biomass based torrefaction pellets is 2 times higher than pulp sludge derived torrefaction pellets, the positive cash flow is observed only after 10 years. This is mainly because of the higher production costs of Case1. The same for Case5 was 11 years. The positive cash flow for Case6 was reached in 8 years, which is lowest among all other cases. The higher cash flow rate for Case5 and Case6 is mainly because of the higher additional revenue through VFA selling. Additionally, for Case6, the increased product flow rate is the main reason for the better cash flow.

3.2.4. Influence on the biomethane and VFA selling price

The proposed process integration approach also allows to produce

biomethane and VFA at reduced price compared with conventional processes. In order to understand the economic benefit of the integrated approach, the MSP of biomethane and VFA was evaluated keeping the TB pellets selling price constant. Fig. 7 presents the MSP of biomethane and VFA at varied TB pellets selling price. The biomethane selling price (Case4) can be reduced to less than 1 €/m³, if torrefied pellets selling price is higher than 230 €/t. At a TB pellets selling price of 260 €/t, the biomethane selling price can be reduced up to 0.15 €/m³. To highlight, today, the market price of wood pellets is varying between 200 and 500 €/t depending on the country. In case of VFA, for Case5, the VFA price can be reduced to 0.97 €/kg at a TB pellets selling price of 260 €/t. Interestingly, for Case6, where energy is supplied by existing pulp mill, the VFA price can be reduced up to 0.07 €/kg to reach the breakeven at a TB pellets selling price of 260 €/t.

3.2.5. Sensitive analysis

The Figs. 8 and 9 show the sensitivity analysis of various operating parameters on the MSP and NPV values of different scenarios, respectively. The moisture content of the sludge showed significant influence on the MSP and NPV values, especially for pulp sludge torrefaction. For wood torrefaction (Case1), the MSP increased from 407 to 499 €/t when the initial moisture content increased by 25%. The same reduced to 353 €/t when moisture content reduced by 25%. In case of pulp sludge standalone torrefaction (Case2), the MSP varied between 152 and 275 €/t when moisture content in the sludge varied between -25% and +25%, respectively. For Case5 and Case6, the influence of moisture was significantly higher compared with other cases. The MSP for Case5 and Case6 varied by 4 and 2 times, respectively, when moisture content varied between +25 and -25%. For Case6, the MSP value is reduced to

Fig. 5. The internal rate on return (IRR) and net present values (NPV) for different cases (a) IRR (b) NPV.

Fig. 6. Cumulative cash flow for different cases. For Case1 torrefied pellets selling price was 450 €/t. For Case2–6 torrefied pellets selling price was 220 €/t.

Fig. 7. The variation in the minimum selling price of biomethane and volatile fatty acids (VFA) at fixed selling price of torrefied pellets. (a) biomethane selling price (b) VFA selling price for Case5, (c) VFA selling price for Case6.

54 €/t from 72 €/t (for base case) when moisture content reduced by 25% (i.e. from 60 to 45 wt.%). The same trend can also be observed in NPV values, where it increased from -3.62 M€ to 21.06 M€ for Case5, and 1.27 M€ to 30.08 M€ for Case6 respectively at TB pellets selling price of 220 €/t, when moisture content altered from +25% to -25%. The increased energy input and reduced product flow are the main reasons for the higher fluctuations in economic parameters with varying moisture content. Next to moisture content, the VFA selling price showed influence on the MSP and NPV values, when VFA selling price is increased by 25% (i.e. 2.5 €/kg), MSP value reduced to 24 €/t for Case6, which is the lowest selling price observed. At the same conditions, the NPV reached to 24 M€ with an IRR of 18% at TB pellets selling price of 220 €/t.

The total fixed capital costs also showed influence on the overall economic feasibility. The other parameters, such as biomethane selling price, electrical energy, heat energy prices showed limited influence on the economic parameters. Previous studies observed that feedstock price

is the most influencing price on the economic feasibility of the torrefaction process. In this study, as pulp sludge is available at no-cost, this factor doesn't have any effect on pulp sludge torrefaction.

Previous study on the torrefaction of roadside grass observed that gate fee also showed significant influence on the economic performance. However, in this study, the influence of gate fee is limited as the gate fee was selected as 5 €/t of sludge compared with previous study i.e. 25 €/t.

3.3. Life cycle assessment

Fig. 10 shows the global warming potential (GWP) for different cases. The GWP values were 1002, 1149, 1272, 1282, 1314, and 1502 kg CO₂ eq./ton of TB pellets for Case1, Case2, Case3, Case4, Case5 and Case6, respectively. The forestry-based torrefaction showed lower emissions compared with pulp sludge torrefaction. This is mainly because of the higher energy input during the drying. In the pulp sludge torrefaction Case2 (standalone) showed lower emissions compared with integrated approaches. Interestingly, the VFA production showed higher GWP values compared with other cases. For example, Case5 has 3.3 and 2.5% higher emissions than Case3 and Case4, respectively. The primary reason is the higher heat energy input for VFA recovery. The heat energy for drying and torrefaction is the major source of emissions in both, forestry biomass and pulp sludge torrefaction, which are accounted for 67% and 82% for standalone forestry biomass torrefaction (Case1) and pulp sludge torrefaction (Case2), respectively. In case of VFA production, 27% of emissions are coming from heat energy for VFA recovery.

Previously, Thengane et al. [36] observed the GWP values in the range of 0.033 to 0.043 kg CO₂ eq. per MJ of torrefied rice husk. In another study, Adams et al. [37] observed around 0.0175 kg CO₂ eq. per MJ in case of scots pine torrefaction. In this study, the GWP for standalone torrefaction of forestry biomass and pulp sludge was 0.04 and 0.05 kg CO₂ eq. per MJ, respectively.

4. Summary

In this study, for the first time, techno-economic and environmental feasibility of using pulp sludge as a feedstock in torrefaction as an alternative to forestry biomass was presented. Additionally, for the first time, overall feasibility of integrating pulp sludge torrefaction with anaerobic digestion to produce biomethane and volatile fatty acids was presented. The first observation is that, the minimum selling price of torrefied biomass pellets can be reduced from 407 to 185 €/t in case of pulp sludge standalone torrefaction compared with forestry biomass torrefaction, which is 2.2 times lower. Today the market price of wood pellets for industry are around 147, 226 and 538 €/t in Estonia, Latvia and Austria respectively [21,38]. At the same time API2 Rotterdam coal price is around 331 €/t [39]. In comparison with wood pellets and coal, the pulp sludge derived torrefied pellets have lower selling price even without considering the subsidies. The torrefied biomass pellets selling price can be further reduced if pulp sludge torrefaction is integrated with anaerobic digestion. For example, in case of volatile fatty acids production from torrefaction condensate, the MSP of torrefied pellets can be reduced to 163 €/t. However, in the integrated approaches biogas production from torrefaction condensate and its subsequent utilization in either energy production through engine or upgrading to biomethane did not show better economic feasibility without subsidies like feed-in tariff compared with standalone pulp sludge torrefaction. In case if the torrefaction is integrated with existing pulp mill to share the heat energy requirement, the MSP of torrefied pellets can be reduced as low as 72 €/t.

The moisture content of the sludge is the main influencing factor on the overall economic feasibility of the pulp sludge torrefaction. In general, the initial moisture content of the sludge is > 90 wt.%. and it is of paramount importance to reduce it to less than 70% through mechanical methods prior to drying. The moisture content effects the process in two ways 1) increases the dryer capacity and drying energy input, and

Fig. 8. Sensitivity analysis of different parameters on the minimum selling price of torrefied pellets (€/t).

ultimately increases the both investment and operational costs; 2) relatively reduces the product flow because of lower dry solids flow to the torrefaction process. For example, the selling price of pellets increased from 185 €/t to 275 €/t when initial moisture content varied from 60 to 75%. At the same time the selling price can be reduced to 163 €/t in case of standalone pulp sludge torrefaction (Case2) and to 92 €/t for Case5 (VFA production) when moisture content reduced from 60 to 45%. Interestingly, the selling price of pulp sludge derived pellets at such high moisture content is still lower than the forestry biomass as there is no operational costs on feedstock. However, thermal drying of sludge with such high water content may not be energy efficient and also environmentally feasible. The mechanical dewatering, like filter press and centrifuge decanters, could reduce the moisture content to 50 – 60 wt.% of total solids.

Sharing of resources between different processes could be helpful to improve the economic feasibility of bio-based products. If pulp mill supplies the heat energy needed for drying and torrefaction through its existing boiler, the minimum selling price of pellets can be reduced to as low as 54 €/t. This is 6 times lower than the present market price of coal, 10 times less than the wood pellets price in central Europe and 4 times less than the wood pellets price in Estonia. Because of today's higher inflation rates, the investment costs are much higher in this study compared with previous studies. To highlight, the chemical engineering plant cost index (CEPCI) increased from 596.2 in 2020 to 803.6 in June 2022. In case if fixed capital investment could be reduced by 25%, the

minimum selling price of torrefied biomass pellets can be reduced to 150 €/t from 189 €/t for standalone pulp sludge torrefaction. The share of boiler is around 16% in the total invest on equipment (Case2). This investment on boiler could be reduced in case if heat energy is supplied by the pulp mill. However, it is important to highlight that the significance of these benefits depends on the price of heat energy that pulp mill charges.

Gate fee is the other parameter which could show significant influence on the economics of waste handling processes. In this study, for conservative calculations, the gate fee is selected as 5 €/t. In Estonia, the land fill gate fee for biodegradable wastes varies between 20 and 48 €/t [40]. The previous studies on the economic feasibility of municipal waste pyrolysis [18] and road side grass torrefaction [34] also considered a gate fee of 50 and 25 €/t respectively. If the gate fee is charged as 20 € per ton of pulp sludge, the minimum selling price of pellets can be reduced to 118, 143, 135, 78, and 12 €/t for Case2, Case3, Case4, Case5 and Case6 respectively. In terms of energy the minimum selling price is around 8.5 and 5 €/GJ for gate fee of 5 and 20 €/t of sludge respectively, in case of pulp sludge based standalone torrefaction (Case2). Previously [34], reported a value of 4.8 €/GJ for road side grass torrefaction and integrated with anaerobic digestion and at a gate fee of 25 €/t.

The selection of utility fuel also has significant influence in the pulp sludge torrefaction. In this study, in order to make it as an independent process, the dried pulp sludge was considered as utility fuel. This resulted in the low product yield, especially in case of integrating it with

Fig. 9. Sensitivity analysis of different parameters on the net present values (M€) of different cases at a torrefied pellets selling price of 200 €/t.

anaerobic digestion. In the today's market scenario, neither natural gas nor coals are viable as utility fuels because of their high prices. Alternatively, the wood waste available at pulp mill could be considered as utility fuel. In addition, integrating with solar drying could also be beneficial in terms of economic and environmental feasibility.

The proposed approach of integrating pulp sludge torrefaction with anaerobic digestion also allows to reduce the selling price of biomethane and VFA. For example, at a fixed selling price of 250 €/ton of torrefied pellets, the selling price of biomethane and VFA can be reduced to 0.44 €/m³ (i.e. 42 €/MWh) and 1.07 €/kg of VFA, where the market prices are around 199 €/MWh and 2 €/kg of VFA. These values are for base cases i.e. (Case4 and Case5). In case of reduced moisture content, and increased gate fee, these prices could be further reduced significantly. Finally, the best strategy could be the combination of dewatering the sludge to < 60% through mechanical methods, charging a gate fee > 10 €/ton of sludge and heat energy sharing with existing pulp mill boiler.

In case of environmental feasibility, the stand alone pulp sludge torrefaction (Case2) showed higher (15%) emissions compared with forestry biomass torrefaction (Case1). This is mainly because of the higher energy input for drying the sludge. It is worth to note that the combustion of torrefaction volatiles and dried sludge as utility fuel was considered for heat energy production. Thus, the CO₂ emissions from combustion are biogenic. Some LCA studies don't consider these emissions in the impact assessment. However, as these emissions are going to

stay for long time in the environment, in this study the biogenic CO₂ emissions are also included in the impact assessment. If the dried wood chips and pulp sludge could be replaced with natural gas as utility fuel, the emissions can be reduced significantly, especially in case of integrated process (i.e. Case3 – Case6). The integrated process of Case5 and Case6 (VFA production) showed higher emissions because of higher energy input for the VFA recovery. Diverting the heat energy recovered from torrefied biomass cooling and torrefaction volatiles condensation could help to reduce the external heat energy demand and there by ultimately could help to reduce the emissions.

The author also wants to highlight that, if the CO₂ emissions savings from heat energy recovery, electrical energy production and land filling of pulp sludge are considered, then the net CO₂ emissions from proposed sludge handling could be reduced significantly. At the same time, the GWP of acetic acid production from methanol carbonylation is around 1.4 – 1.8 kg CO₂ eq. per kg of acetic acid produced [41]. In that regard considering emission savings for VFA production from renewable sources could further reduce the net emissions for Case5 and Case6.

Although the economic feasibility is attractive, there could be some operational challenges, especially in case of integrated processes. The AD of torrefaction condensate need to be studied at pilot scale to better understand the operational challenges. The downstream processing of VFA produced from torrefaction condensate could also be challenging, which needs to be studied. The overall feasibility of the proposed process also needs to be compared with other methods commonly used in pulp

Fig. 10. Climate change impact for different cases a) per ton of pellets of production b) per MJ energy of torrefied pellets.

sludge handling, which is the subject of our future study.

To conclude, using pulp sludge as an alternative feedstock to the forestry biomass improves the economic feasibility of torrefaction process. Integrating it further with anaerobic digestion could allow to minimize the selling price of bioenergy carriers and biochemical and thereby, improves their overall economic feasibility. The proposed process addressed different challenges in biobased products production i.e. finding low cost or no-cost alternative feedstock to forestry wood, alternative application of torrefaction process, sustainable handling and resource recovery from pulp industry sludge, and producing bioenergy carriers and biochemicals at improved economic and environmental feasibility. The proposed approach also allows to share the resources between different industries under the concept of industrial symbiosis and improves the resource efficiency.

5. Conclusion

This study evaluated the economic feasibility of pulp sludge torrefaction and further integrating it with anaerobic digestion. The torrefied pellets selling price can be reduced by 2.2 times for pulp sludge based torrefaction compared with forestry biomass based standalone torrefaction. For improved economic feasibility, the moisture content of the pulp sludge needs to be reduced to a minimum level of 60% through mechanical dewatering. The economic feasibility also depended on resource sharing with existing pulp mill either in terms of money as a gate fee or through process heat energy supply. In case of integrated approach, the volatile fatty acids production showed better economic

feasibility than biomethane production. In case of environmental feasibility, pulp sludge torrefaction with volatile fatty acids (VFA) production showed higher emissions compared with other cases because of higher energy input at VFA recovery. To conclude, using pulp sludge as an alternative feedstock to forestry biomass in torrefaction and further integrating it with anaerobic digestion could allow to produce energy carriers and biochemicals at improved economic competitiveness.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tharaka Rama Krishna C. Doddapaneni: Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation.
Timo Kikas: Conceptualization, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability

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